

InterAgency Institute
BEYOND INSTITUTIONAL BOUNDARIES

Report

I Conferência Intersectorial sobre Armas Autônomas Letais, Inteligência Artificial e a Lusofonia

Lisbon, July 11, 2022

Authors: Ana Paula Rodriguez, Ana Beatriz Duarte, Juliana Martins, Luzia Costa Becker

Support

**Stop Killer Robots Campaign
Lusophone University of Lisbon**

* This is a machine translation from the original document in Portuguese:
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1AggDAICAc2ASBUol4t-zhQzMLBUSI63b/edit?usp=sharing&oid=112384637287094855762&rtpof=true&sd=true>

**CAMPAIGN TO STOP
KILLER ROBOTS**

UNIVERSIDADE
LUSÓFONA

Who are we?

Founded in October 2020, the InterAgency Institute is a digital Think Tank created from a network of researchers from the Global South across the world. It is focused on the development of studies that can contribute to policies to strengthen institutional engagements, in Europe and the Americas, for the benefit of human rights, peace, security and cooperation. The approach is focused on some specific dimensions, such as information transfer, construction of decision-making processes, construction of policies and operational structures. We research, propose and modulate knowledge for the benefit of sustainable, innovative and responsible development in the area of security.

Proposal

In 2021, the InterAgency Institute joined the international campaign [Stop Killer Robots](#), whose objective is to pressure the creation of a new International Law that regulates the autonomy in the systems of weapons. The campaign was launched in 2013 and currently has more than 180 members. This, as a form of dissemination, opened a public notice in 2022, to grant funds that would be intended for its members who wanted to promote and disseminate the Stop Killer Robots proposal.

The InterAgency Institute submitted a proposal which provided for the promotion of an event that would involve academics, students, government entities that could discuss topics on the use of lethal autonomous weapons and artificial intelligence. After evaluation by the Campaign Committee, the InterAgency Institute proposal was approved and awarded with the amount of US\$ 4,000, which was used to pay technicians, travel expenses, accommodation, transport, meals, among other items described in the expense report.

Our focus for the event was based on the need for discussion on the topic within the scope of the Community of Portuguese Speaking Countries (CPLP), given that in 2021, the 6th Review Conference of the UN Convention on Conventional Weapons (CCW) will not managed to pass the proposal to create legal instruments aimed at a total ban on the use of lethal autonomous weapons. Despite this, the topic continues to be debated within the framework of the Group of Government Experts on Emerging Technologies. According to a recent publication by the InterAgency Institute, the issue requires “a

multisectoral approach". According to the study, "countries not central to the weapons production system can represent an important force for public and political pressure."

The conference

The support of Universidade Lusófona de Lisboa was essential for the event to take place. The university provided us with the entire physical structure, providing us with a movie theater, audio-visual equipment, an intern who was responsible for online and face-to-face broadcasts, chairs for the guests and a pulpit for the moderators. In addition, it provided us with printed materials and we were able to rely on the structure of the university restaurant for food, paid for with resources from the event, the team and coffee break items.

The objective of the event was to generate awareness and collaboration with the various countries of the Portuguese-speaking community regarding the manufacture, use and regulation of lethal drones not supervised by humans. With this, we seek to strengthen the role of the community in the field of academic research, reinforcing its representation in international political proposals that focus on solutions originating in the Global South.

The IA team was divided into different roles to run all stages of the event. In the initial moment, we defined the public to which the event would be destined and the guests were selected according to criteria of ethnicity, gender and representation in the CPLP.

It should be noted that among the guests were military, academics, jurists, representatives of civil society and governments. We also carefully invited António Guterres, Portuguese and current UN Secretary General, to collaborate in some way with our event, since his position is public against the use of lethal autonomous weapons. We had a response by email from a spokesman for Guterres, but in the sense of congratulating us on our achievement, which showed us the importance of our proposal.

We also sent an invitation to Pope Francis, as we wanted a position from the Catholic Church on the subject. However, this message was not returned, but we think that, somehow, the objective of propagating ideas has had the desired effects.

Organizers

Ana Beatriz Duarte (France) - University of Coimbra - General Coordination/mediator
Ana Paula Rodriguez (Brazil) – InterAgency Institute - Team coordination/mediator
Sabrina Medeiros (Portugal) – Lusophone University/InterAgency Institute - Institutional articulator/debater
Juliana Martins (Italy) – InterAgency Institute - External Relations/debater
Luzia Costa Becker (Germany) – InterAgency Institute - Glossary author/debater
Izabella Ávilla(Brazil) - InterAgency Institute - Glossary author/Ceremonial
Luís Campani (Portugal) - InterAgency Institute - Glossary Designer/Volunteer Team
Thiago Honório (Brazil) - InterAgency Institute - Technical support for online transmission

Catarina Grácio (Portugal) - InterAgency Institute - Proofreader and research during the preparation of the proposal

Volunteer Team (all students from Universidade Lusófona de Lisboa):

Beatriz Costa
Samuel Martins
Danielle Iriart
Bruno Atella
João Sousa
Camila Pacheco (certificates design)
Gabriela Costa
Luíza Malachias

Dissemination

After the confirmation of our guests to speak, we started the dissemination with the launch of a Newsletter to the press, universities, students, government agencies, International Organizations and NGOs.

As part of the dissemination strategy, we produced different informative materials such as the Glossary Stop Killers Robots: autonomous weapons systems, registered with DOI on the Zenodo platform.

Universidade Lusófona created a page for the event on its website and sent direct mail to the internal community: <https://www.ulusofona.pt/agenda/armas-autonomas-letais> . And the InterAgency Institute also dedicated a page to the event: <http://interagency.institute/events/14-events/66-autonomous-weapons.html> (https://interagency.institute/?page_id=384)

We Could also publish an opinion editorial on 06/30/2022 of in the newspaper O Público, one of the mos important media outlet from Portugal, entitled “[A guerra do futuro em debate no presente](#)”, written by the researchers Ana Beatriz Duarte and Sabrina Medeiros.

The academic events website Plataforma 9 released our conference: <https://plataforma9.com/congressos/conferencia-armas-autonomas-letais-inteligencia-artificial-lusofonia>

Members of the InsterAgency Institute publicized the event on their personal and professional networks, in addition to specialized groups on Facebook.

We created a form for the registration of participants: bit.ly/ArmasAutonomas

We sent informative newsletters and also to publicize materials related to the event to the list of interested parties and also to the institutional mailing of the InterAgency Institute of about 250 contacts.

We wrote to Universities in CPLP countries asking for outreach support to potential stakeholders in their internal networks.

Agenda

On July 11, 2022, from 11 am to 5 pm (Portugal and Angola time, GMT+1), from 7 am to 1 pm (Brazil time) in the cinema auditorium of Universidade Lusófona de Lisboa, the event took place in a hybrid format with the following schedule (in person and online, via the Zoom platform). .

The event was broadcast on the YouTube channel of Universidade Lusófona.

Opening session (11h-11:30h)

Sabrina Medeiros - Prof. from Lusophone University and researcher at the InterAgency Institute

Sergio Vieira da Silva - Director of the Degree in Security Studies, Lusophone University

Fernando Campos - Director of the Masters in Political Science, Lusophone University

Ana Beatriz Duarte - PhD candidate at the University of Coimbra

Film Screening“[Immoral Code](#)”, followed by a debate by the researchers of the InterAgency Institute, Ana Paula Rodriguez, Juliana Martins e Luzia Costa Becker (11:30h-12:30h)

Lunch break(12:30h-13:30h)

Panel 1: Artificial Intelligence and Human Rights: challenges of emerging technologies (13:30h-15h)

Speakers:

Vasco Malta (Portugal) - Head of Mission of the International Organization for Migration (IOM) in Portugal

- Migrações e inteligência artificial

Emellin de Oliveira (Portugal) - Executive Coordinator of NOVA Refugee Clinic - Legal Clinic, Faculty of Law, NOVA University of Lisbon

- Inteligência artificial e digitalização da gestão migratória: que impactos para os direitos humanos?

Guedson C. Rompão (Cabo Verde) - Chairman of the Board of Directors of the Center for African Studies for Development and Innovation, CEADI

- Que direitos humanos a inteligência artificial reforça ou diminui? O contexto de Cabo Verde

Milton Meza Rivas (Spain) - United Nations Consultant

- Los sistemas de armas autónomas letales: un desafío para el derecho internacional humanitario, la seguridad y el desarme (apresentação em espanhol)

Mediator: Ana Paula Rodriguez - Researcher at the InterAgency Institute

Comments: Maria Francisca Saraiva, University of Lisbon

Break (15h-15:30h)

Panel 2: Artificial Intelligence and War: territorial implications, legal responsibilities and ethical-moral imperatives (15:30-17h)

Speakers:

Inês Godinho (Portugal) - Professor at the Lusophone University of Porto

- Inteligência artificial e ciberguerra

Bengue Gonçalo Manuel (Angola) - Lieutenant Colonel, Institute of National Defense, IDN

- Hasta la vista, sapiens: abordagem geral sobre armas autônomas

Karina Domingues Bressan Vidal (Brazil) - General Coordination of Digital Transformation, Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation

- Transformação digital e inteligência artificial: uma agenda para a sociedade digital

Sandra Becker (Brazil) - Vice-director of the Institute of International Relations and Defense of the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro, IRID/UFRJ

- Drones sob a ética e a estratégia platônicas

Eduardo Mariutti (Brazil) - Associate Professor at the Institute of Economics at the State University of Campinas, Unicamp, and at the San Tiago Dantas Graduate Program

- O olho da guerra: digitalização e metamorfose da percepção. A matematização do campo visual e os sistemas de vigilância e controle contemporâneos

Mediator: Ana Beatriz Duarte - PhD candidate at the University of Coimbra

Closing (17h-17:15h)

Participants bios

Vasco Malta is head of mission of the United Nations International Organization for Migration (IOM) in Portugal. He is a lawyer and Latin Legum Magister in European Law in a Global Context from the Católica School of Law. In 2009 he was appointed national liaison officer for the European Agency for Fundamental Rights of the European Union, where he coordinated the network of EU National Liaison Officers, in addition to other projects. He was Assistant to the High Commissioner for Migration and Director for International Relations, Migration Policy and Migration Capture at the High Commissioner for Migration. In 2019, he was appointed Deputy Minister of Internal Affairs for the areas of migration, refugees, human trafficking and domestic violence and was appointed as an adviser to the Commission for Equality and Against Racial Discrimination.

Emellin de Oliveira is executive coordinator and co-founder of NOVA Refugee Clinic – Legal Clinic, in which she leads the research line Migration and Digital Transformation. She is a researcher at the Center for Research in Law and Society (CEDIS) and a PhD candidate in Law at NOVA School of Law, with an investigation into the influence of security issues on Migration Law

in the European Union. She has a master's degree in International Migration from ISCTE-IUL; young auditor in National Defense by the National Defense Institute – IDN; postgraduate degree in Human Rights from Ius Gentium Conimbrigae and in International Relations from the University of Coimbra; and graduated in Law from the Federal University of Ceará.

Guedson C. Rompão is president of the Center for African Studies for Development and Innovation (CEADI) and coordinator of the Ciência na Mon Project, funded by the Joint Office of UNDP, UNFPA and UNICEF Cape Verde. He is a member of the organizing committee of the CPLP Young Investigators Meeting. He holds a degree in Law from the University of Santiago and in Administration and Finance from the Politécnica de Formação Profissional. He also has training in Human Resource Management and Human Rights. He is a volunteer at the African Center for Democracy and Human Rights Studies (ACDHRS) and a founding member of the Lusophone Human Rights Platform.

Milton Mezas Rivas is a senior adviser at the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA). He is a researcher at DIAR, application of artificial intelligence and robotics in 21st century global society and its impact on Law (University of Barcelona). He was an external consultant in the Peace Talks during the peace process in Syria and worked as a diplomatic official (Charge d'Affaires and Minister Counselor) of Venezuela before the International Criminal Court, the Special Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia and the International Court of Justice (The Hague, Netherlands). He was also a delegate to the Human Rights Council and the United Nations Conference on Disarmament. Among others, he wrote “The lethal autonomous weapons: a challenge for the international humanitarian right, human rights, security and international disarmament” and “Autonomy in future military and security technologies. Implications for law, peace, and conflict”.

Inês Fernandes Godinho is an associate professor at the Universidade Lusófona do Porto (ULP), where she is also director of the Law Degree at the Faculty of Law and Political Science. She is also director of the ULP Law Review / ULP Law Review, president of the ULP Ethics Committee and a member of the National Ethics Council for Life Sciences (CNECV), integrating its Coordinating Committee. He is also a member of the Instituto Jurídico (Faculty of Law of the University of Coimbra) and of CEAD Francisco Suárez (Universidade Lusófona), where he coordinates the Law, Life and Technology research line, within which he has developed research on Artificial Intelligence. She is the author of more than 50 legal titles, published in Portugal and abroad.

Bengue Gonçalo Manuel is a lieutenant colonel and a member of the National Defense Institute of Angola. He is head of the Department of Telecommunications and Information Technologies at the National Directorate of Telecommunications and Information Technologies (DNTI) of the Ministry of National Defense and Veterans of the Homeland of Angola. He worked as a Telecommunications and Informatics Officer at the then Military

Academy of Angola. He holds a Master in Telecommunications in the Specialty of Satellite and Broadcasting Systems from the Russian Army Telecommunications Academy in St.

Karina Domingues Bressan Vidal is a Science and Technology Analyst at the General Coordination of Digital Transformation, Secretariat of Entrepreneurship and Innovation at the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation of Brazil, where she works on the Brazilian Strategy for Digital Transformation (E-digital); Brazilian Artificial Intelligence Strategy (EBIA); Internet of Things (IoT) Plan; and with Thematic Chambers 4.0 (Industry, Smart Cities, Agro, Health and Tourism). She holds a PhD in Science Education and a Master's in Knowledge Management and Information Technology. She is an industrial electrical engineer and holds a BA in Mathematics Applied to Computer Science.

Sandra Becker is deputy director of the Institute of International Relations and Defense of the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (IRID/UFRJ) and coordinator of the Decania Extension of the Center for Legal and Economic Sciences (CCJE/UFRJ). She is a professor and researcher for the degree courses in Defense and International Strategic Management and International Relations at UFRJ. She is part of the Ethics Committee in Research with Human Beings at UFRJ. She holds a degree and a master's degree in Nursing from UFRJ and a PhD in Bioethics, Applied Ethics and Collective Health from Fundação Oswaldo Cruz. She is co-author of “Smart Weapons in Cyberspace: Innovative Opportunities and Pressing Challenges” and “Remote Threat: The Relationship between Distance and Decision Making in the Use of Lethal Force in Drone Airstrikes”.

Eduardo Barros Mauritti is an associate professor at Unicamp's Institute of Economics and at the San Tiago Dantas Graduate Program. He is a member of the Research Network in Strategic Autonomy, Technology and Defense, funded by the Project Incorporation of Aerospace Technology for Defense: organizational, doctrinal and strategic autonomy impacts (Unicamp, Unesp, Unifa). He is the author of, among other texts, “War, complexity and information: automation of perception and predictive surveillance systems” and “The machines of vision: automation of perception, predictive surveillance and social control”.

Data and results

The event had:

- Organization team with 9 main members, in addition to other collaborators, distributed among Brazil, Portugal, France, Germany and Italy
- 9 speakers

- 5 countries represented: Brazil, Portugal, Angola, Cape Verde and Spain (although the event prioritizes Lusophony, we consider the participation of the speaker Milton Meza Rivas, from Spain, of great importance, as he is a UN consultant on the subject)
- 168 interested parties, registered through the form available in the dissemination channels
- About 25 gifts, from Portugal, Brazil and Angola; 88 participants on the Zoom platform and 213 views on Youtube (277 as of August 15, 2022)

On the sectoral representation of the speakers:

- 2 speakers from International Organizations
- 4 lecturers from universities
- 1 research institution speaker
- 1 military organization speaker
- 1 government representative speaker (ministry)

About invited institutions (52):

- Universities from all CPLP countries
- Military institutions of CPLP countries
- International Organizations (such as Amnesty International)
- Research institutions
- Government representations
- Ambassadors (such as Flávio Damico - Brazil)
- Members of the Stop Killer Robots Campaign (of these we did not join the collaboration)
- Press

Performance of add via LinkedIn, with paid ad for July 3rd and 4th:

Newsletters performance:

Outputs

- Initial concept note prepared in Portuguese and English, used to invite speakers.
 - Opinion article in the newspaper O Público, from Portugal, entitled “[The war of the future in debate in the present](#)” (translated), written by the researchers Sabrina Medeiros and Ana Beatriz Duarte
 - [Glossary](#) Stop Killer Robots: autonomous weapons systems, authored by researchers Luzia Costa Becker and Izabella Ávilla, with diagramming by researcher Luis Campani
 - A [Policy Brief](#) in three languages
 - A Final Report
 - Video transmission and recording on Youtube of Universidade Lusófona: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Llbg36grvY> , with about 270 views until the end of July 2022; 213 total views on the day of the conference.
 - Screening of the documentary Immoral Code for the Portuguese public
 - Video generation of the event on the InterAgency Institute's Youtube channel, with around 20 views by the end of July 2022.
- Part 1: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=y3JrmukpPGg>
- Part 2: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZwS2ED2nsl8>

Post-event

The organizing team met on July 22, 2022 to assess the results and process of organizing the event. We also discussed next steps and the holding of a second conference on the topic in another Portuguese-speaking country. Some practical decisions include: the elaboration of a guide for the organization of events, with the lessons learned from this experience; eventual production of podcasts and policy briefs with some of the speakers; procedure for certifying participants, speakers, organizers and volunteers; IA participation in the GGE/CCW meeting in Geneva, 25-29 July 2022.

After the event in Lisbon, the InterAgency Institute had the opportunity to participate, as a member of the Stop Killer Robots campaign, in the second session of the 2022 Group of Governmental Experts (GGE) on emerging technologies in the area of lethal autonomous weapons systems (LAWS), which met at the Palace of Nations in Geneva from 25 to 29 July. Researcher Ana Beatriz Duarte attended the sessions on July 28 and 29, when she was able to better understand the dynamics of the negotiations and strengthen ties with country representatives and campaign staff, with a view to greater and more intense collaboration with the interAgency Institute.

In addition, we highlight the invitation made by Guedson Rompão, director of the Center for African Studies for Development and Innovation (CEADI), for institutional support of the I National Human Rights Forum of Cabo Verde, which took place on August 23 and 24, 2022. The InterAgency Institute promptly provided institutional support, as well as participated in the exhibition of works by researchers Luzia Costa Becker, Sabrina Medeiros and Ana Paula Rodriguez. This participation, as a result, proved to be quite positive, as it solidifies one of the main objectives of our event to create integration with the CPLP countries.

Images

Organizers, speakers and volunteers.

Opening session

Debate after screening of Immoral Code

Pannel 1

Pannel 2

Audience

Closure

Sample of social media card

I CONFERÊNCIA INTERSETORIAL SOBRE Armas autónomas letais, inteligência artificial e a lusofonia

#PalestranteConfirmada

Sandra Becker

Instituto de Relações Internacionais e Defesa da
Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro, IRID/UFR

Inscrições: <https://bit.ly/ArmasAutonomas>

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Sample of social media card

O InterAgency Institute e a Universidade Lusófona, com o apoio da campanha **Stop Killer Robots**, promovem um importante debate sobre armas autónomas capazes de tomar decisões de atirar sem precisar da interferência de humanos. A conferência reunirá representantes da academia, governo, sociedade civil e militares de países de língua portuguesa.

Abertura: 11h GMT+1 (Portugal e Angola) | 7h GMT-3 (Brasil). Estreia do documentário **Immoral Code**.

Mesas: 13h GMT+1 (Portugal e Angola) | 9h GMT-3 (Brasil)

Local: Sala de cinema da Universidade Lusófona - Campo Grande, 376, Lisboa, Portugal + Plataforma digital Zoom

Inscrição obrigatória. Em breve divulgaremos a programação da conferência.

[Faça sua inscrição](#)

Conteúdos relacionados >>>

Glossário

Entenda o que são os "robôs assassinos" e outros termos usados para descrever a questão das armas autónomas letais neste glossário produzido especialmente para a conferência.

[Faça do download »](#)

Immoral Code

A campanha internacional **Stop Killer Robots** fez um documentário sobre os "robôs assassinos". O filme será exibido pela primeira vez em Portugal na abertura da conferência, em 11 de julho.

[Inscriva-se para assistir ao filme \(online ou presencial\) »](#)

info@interagencyinstitute

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O InterAgency Institute certifica a

Vasco Malta

a participação como palestrante com a apresentação "Migrações e Inteligência Artificial" na Conferência Intersetorial "Armas Autónomas Letais, Inteligência Artificial e a Lusofonia", em 11 de julho de 2022.

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Assinado por: **SABRINA EVANGELISTA MEDEIROS**
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Sabrina Medeiros

Professora da Universidade Lusófona de Lisboa

Certificate design